

Basic Local Alignment Search Tool(BLAST) of isolated Sars-Cov-2 genome using Biopython scripts at windows

SUBASH S

ABSTRACT:

Blast is performed to find regions of similarity between sequences. Severe acute respiratory related corona virus isolated coding sequences is collected to find the sequences of similarity by using BLAST. This Basic local alignment is performed by using scripts of Biopython. The output of the blast are examined and filtered by using Biopython scripts at windows.

Keywords: Corona virus, BLAST, Biopython.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Biopython is the most popular molecular biology package for computation. Brad Chapman and Jeff Chang developed it in 1999. It is mainly written in python but some C code is there to solve complex optimization. The Biopython Project is an international association of developers of freely available Python tools for computational molecular biology, Bioinformatics. Python is an object oriented, interpreted, flexible language that is becoming more popular for scientific computing. Python is easy to learn, has a very clear syntax and can easily be extended with modules written in C, C++ or FORTRAN, PEARL. Biopython scripts are easy to learn and understand compared to Pearl. Biological sequence identification is an integral part of bioinformatics. Several tools are available for this, each with their own algorithms and approaches, such as BLAST, FASTA, HMMER, and many more. In general, these tools usually use your sequence to search a database of potential matches. With the growing number of potential matches, interpreting the results becomes increasingly hard as there could be hundreds or even thousands of potential matches. This hurdle can be overcome by using scripts. Naturally, manual interpretation of these searches' results is out of the question. Moreover, you often need to work with several sequence search tools, each with its own statistics, conventions, and output format. Imagine how daunting it would be when you need to work with multiple sequences using multiple search tools. So, we can examine and filter this large number of data using biopython. Biopython is capable of a lot like it can do protein structure, sequence motifs, sequence

alignment also machine learning. Biopython has a lot of libraries for the help of biologists in their work as it is portable, easy, and clear. In some cases Google images use Biopython, BioPerl, BioJAVA, BioRuby are the siblings of the Biopython project. The goal of Biopython is to provide simple, standard and extensive access to bioinformatics through python language. The specific goals of the Biopython are Providing standardized access to bioinformatics resources, High-quality, reusable modules and scripts, Fast array manipulation that can be used in Cluster code, PDB, NaiveBayes and Markov Model, Genomic data analysis.

2. METHODS AND RESULTS

2.1 Installation of Biopython

Python includes the package management system "pip" which should allow you to install Biopython (and its dependency NumPy if needed), with the help of pip package we can upgrade or uninstall by using a single command as follows;

pip install biopython: This command installs the Biopython package.

pip install --upgrade biopython: This command upgrades the biopython package.

pip uninstall biopython: This command uninstalls the package.

In order to know whether the biopython package is installed or not, we can use this command to verify;

Biopython -v or Biopython --version: which will display the version of biopython.

2.2 Python Requirements

Biopython is currently supported on the following Python implementations:

- ❖ Python 3.8, 3.8.8
- ❖ Python 11

We currently recommend using Python 3.11 or Python 3.8 for installing Biopython package. In order to check whether the python installed or not, we can run this command to know: `python --version`.

Biopython is currently tested on the following Python implementations:

- ❖ Python 9, 10
- ❖ PyPy3.8 v7.3.11

2.3 Isolation of Corona virus genome

Severe acute respiratory related corona virus (Sars-Cov-2) is isolated from the National Centre of Biotechnology (NCBI). We want to know the similarities between coding sequences, we isolated the coding sequence from the whole genome. The isolated genome can be downloaded in either format fasta or genbank etc.

2.4 BLAST in Biopython

2.4.1 Running BLAST over the internet:

We should use the function `qblast()` in the `Bio.Blast.NCBIWWW` module to call the online version of BLAST. This has three non-optional arguments:

- ❖ The first argument is the blast program to use for the search, as a lower case string. At present, `qblast` works with `blastn`, `blastp`, `blastx`, `tblast` and `tblastx`.
- ❖ The second argument specifies the databases to search against.
- ❖ The third argument is a string containing your query sequence. This can either be the sequence itself, the sequence in fasta format, or an identifier like a GI number.

To know more about the `qblast` function, you can use the following command:

```
>>> from Bio.Blast import NCBIWWW
```

```
>>> help(NCBIWWW.qblast)
```

The above code will give a following output;

```
-----
>>> from Bio.Blast import NCBIWWW
>>> help(NCBIWWW.qblast)
Help on function qblast in module Bio.Blast.NCBIWWW:

qblast(program, database, sequence, url_base='https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi')
    BLAST search using NCBI's QBLAST server or a cloud service provider.

    Supports all parameters of the old qblast API for Put and Get.

    Please note that NCBI uses the new Common URL API for BLAST searches
    on the internet (http://ncbi.github.io/blast-cloud/dev/api.html). Thus,
    some of the parameters used by this function are not (or are no longer)
    officially supported by NCBI. Although they are still functioning, this
    may change in the future.

    The Common URL API (http://ncbi.github.io/blast-cloud/dev/api.html) allows
    doing BLAST searches on cloud servers. To use this feature, please set
    ``url_base='http://host.my.cloud.service.provider.com/cgi-bin/blast.cgi'``
    and ``format_object='Alignment'``. For more details, please see
    https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi?PAGE\_TYPE=BlastDocs&DOC\_TYPE=CloudBlast

    Some useful parameters:

    - program          blastn, blastp, blastx, tblastn, or tblastx (lower case)
    - database         Which database to search against (e.g. "nr").
    - sequence         The sequence to search.
    - ncbi_gi          TRUE/FALSE whether to give 'gi' identifier.
    - descriptions     Number of descriptions to show. Def 500.
    - alignments       Number of alignments to show. Def 500.
    - expect           An expect value cutoff. Def 10.0.
    - matrix_name      Specify an alt. matrix (PAM30, PAM70, BLOSUM80, BLOSUM45).
    - filter           "none" turns off filtering. Default no filtering
    - format_type      "HTML", "Text", "ASN.1", or "XML". Def. "XML".
    - entrez_query     Entrez query to limit Blast search
    - hitlist_size     Number of hits to return. Default 50
    - megablast        TRUE/FALSE whether to use MEga BLAST algorithm (blastn only)
    - short_query      TRUE/FALSE whether to adjust the search parameters for a
                      short query sequence. Note that this will override
                      manually set parameters like word size and e value. Turns
                      off when sequence length is > 30 residues. Default: None.
    - service          plain, psi, phi, rpsblast, megablast (lower case)

    This function does no checking of the validity of the parameters
    and passes the values to the server as is. More help is available at:
    https://ncbi.github.io/blast-cloud/dev/api.html
```

If you have a nucleotide sequence you want to search against the nucleotide database (nt) using BLASTN, and you know the GI number of your query sequence, you can use:

```
>>> from Bio.Blast import NCBIWWW
>>> result_handle = NCBIWWW.qblast("blastn", "nt", "8332116")
```

Since I isolated the coding sequence from the whole genome and saved in a fasta format, I just need to open the file and read in this record as a string, and use that as the query argument by using the following command:

```
>>> from Bio.Blast import NCBIWWW
>>> fasta_string = open("Sars_Cov_2.fasta").read()
#Sars_Cov_2.fasta is our query sequence
>>> result_handle = NCBIWWW.qblast("blastn", "nt", fasta_string)
```

#blastn- nucleotide blast, nt-nucleotide, since my query sequence is nucleotide. If your query sequence is protein, you should enter blastp instead of blastn, p instead of nt , same for every formats

Now that we've got a handle, we are ready to parse the output. The code to parse it is quiet small and easy to understand:

```
>>> blast_record = NCBIXML.read(result_handle)
```

Now, the blast got executed, let's just print out some summary info about all hits in our blast report greater than a particular threshold(E_THRESH_VALUE). The following code does this:

```
>>> E_VALUE_THRESH = 0.04
>>> for alignment in blast_record.alignments:
    for hsp in alignment.hsps:
        if hsp.expect < E_VALUE_THRESH:
            print("*****Alignment*****")
            print("sequence:", alignment.title)
            print("length:", alignment.length)
            print("e value:", hsp.expect)
            print(hsp.query[0:85] + "...")
            print(hsp.match[0:85] + "...")
            print(hsp.sbjct[0:85] + "...")
```

The output of the above command will be shown as;

```
****Alignment****
sequence: gi|255529870|gb|GQ162104.1| Mus musculus anti-beta-amyloid peptide immunoglobulin heavy chain variable region mRNA, partial cds
length: 451
e value: 6.24552e-171
ATGGGCAGRCTTACWCTTTCATTCCTGCTGCTGATTGTCOCCTGCATATGCTTGTGCCAACTTACTCTAAAAGAG...
||||| ||| ||||| ||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||| ||| |||||||||||||||...
ATGGACAGGCTTACTTCTTCATTCCTGCTGCTGATTGTCOCCTGCATATGCTTGTGCCAACTTACTCTAAAAGAG...
****Alignment****
sequence: gi|50365838|gb|AY648632.1| Mus musculus clone SPLH10 immunoglobulin heavy chain variable region mRNA, partial cds
length: 431
e value: 7.6086e-170
ATGGGCAGRCTTACWCTTTCATTCCTGCTGCTGATTGTCOCCTGCATATGCTTGTGCCAACTTACTCTAAAAGAG...
||||| ||| ||||| ||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||| ||| |||||||||||||||...
ATGGACAGGCTTACTTCTTCATTCCTGCTGCTGATTGTCOCCTGCATATGCTTGTGCCAACTTACTCTAAAAGAG...
****Alignment****
sequence: gi|997831424|emb|LT160968.1| Mus musculus IgG2b mRNA for immunoglobulin heavy chain (IgG2b gene), clone Mab23.1.3
length: 1440
e value: 1.37567e-166
ATGGGCAGRCTTACWCTTTCATTCCTGCTGCTGATTGTCOCCTGCATATGCTTGTGCCAACTTACTCTAAAAGAG...
||||| ||| ||||| ||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||| ||| |||||||||||||||...
ATGGACAGGCTTACTTCTTCATTCCTGCTGCTGATTGTCOCCTGCATATGCTTGTGCCAACTTACTCTAAAAGAG...
****Alignment****
sequence: gi|997831420|emb|LT160966.1| Mus musculus IgG1 mRNA for immunoglobulin heavy chain (IgG1 gene), clone Mab19.3.22
length: 1407
e value: 1.67591e-165
ATGGGCAGRCTTACWCTTTCATTCCTGCTGCTGATTGTCOCCTGCATATGCTTGTGCCAACTTACTCTAAAAGAG...
||||| ||| ||||| ||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||| ||| |||||||||||||||...
ATGGACAGGCTTACTTCTTCATTCCTGCTGCTGATTGTCOCCTGCATATGCTTGTGCCAACTTACTCTAAAAGAG...
****Alignment****
sequence: gi|17644232|emb|AJ421677.1| Mus musculus mRNA for immunoglobulin heavy chain, mAb 667
length: 1410
e value: 1.91221e-158
ATGGGCAGRCTTACWCTTTCATTCCTGCTGCTGATTGTCOCCTGCATATGCTTGTGCCAACTTACTCTAAAAGAG...
||||| ||| ||||| ||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||| ||| |||||||||||||||...
ATGGACAGGCTTACTTCTTCATTCCTGCTGCTGATTGTCOCCTGCATATGCTTGTGCCAACTTACTCTAAAAGAG...
****Alignment****
sequence: gi|2489218610|gb|OQ571072.1| Mus musculus clone SC2-92_VH anti-SARS-CoV-2 spike protein immunoglobulin heavy chain variable region mRNA, partial cds
length: 375
e value: 3.45735e-155
GTCCTTGTGCCAACTTACTCTAAAAGAGCTGCGCCCTGGGATATTGAAGCCCTCACAGACCCCTCAGTCTGACTTGT...
||||| ||| ||||| ||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||| ||| |||||||||||||||...
GTCCTTGTGCCAACTTACTCTAAAAGAGCTGCGCCCTGGGATATTGAAGCCCTCACAGACCCCTCAGTCTGACTTGT...
****Alignment****
sequence: gi|995891274|dbj|LC113945.1| Mus musculus mRNA for immunoglobulin gamma heavy chain variable, partial cds, clone: 2H9
length: 414
e value: 1.4701e-153
-----
```

2.4.2 Query result, Hit and High scoring pair(hsp)

The QueryResult object represents a single search query and contains zero or more Hit objects. The output of the blast file will be in XML format and stored in our working directory, Let's see what it looks like using the BLAST file we have:

```
>>> from Bio import SearchIO
>>> blast_qresult = SearchIO.read("my_blast.xml", "blast-xml")
>>> print(blast_qresult)
```

Output:

```
Program: blastn (2.14.1+)
Query: AR648815.1 (483)
Sequence 11 from patent US 6875433
Target: nt
Hits:
-----
# # HSP ID + description
-----
0 1 gi|255529870|gb|GQ162104.1| Mus musculus anti-beta-amy...
1 1 gi|50365838|gb|AY648632.1| Mus musculus clone SPLH10 i...
2 1 gi|997831424|emb|LT160968.1| Mus musculus IgG2b mRNA f...
3 1 gi|997831420|emb|LT160966.1| Mus musculus IgG1 mRNA fo...
4 1 gi|17644232|emb|AJ421677.1| Mus musculus mRNA for immu...
5 1 gi|2489218610|gb|OQ571072.1| Mus musculus clone SC2-92...
6 1 gi|995891274|dbj|LC113945.1| Mus musculus mRNA for imm...
7 1 gi|995891278|dbj|LC113947.1| Mus musculus mRNA for imm...
8 1 gi|50365760|gb|AY648593.1| Mus musculus clone BMH05 im...
9 1 gi|1238799113|gb|KX831510.1| Mus musculus clone H3 ant...
10 1 gi|62533165|gb|BC093517.1| Mus musculus immunoglobulin...
11 1 gi|348969|gb|L22745.1|MUSD Mus musculus immunoglobulin...
12 1 gi|1389531470|gb|MG815651.1| Synthetic construct immun...
13 1 gi|1285895109|gb|MG386918.1| Mus musculus clone AH0P4:...
14 1 gi|1285895101|gb|MG386910.1| Mus musculus clone AH0P4:...
15 1 gi|348976|gb|L22748.1|MUSG Mus musculus immunoglobulin...
16 1 gi|50365870|gb|AY648648.1| Mus musculus clone SPLH26 i...
17 1 gi|62024602|gb|BC092066.1| Mus musculus immunoglobulin...
18 1 gi|15150234|gb|AF393308.1|AF393308 Mus musculus clone ...
19 1 gi|92445964|gb|BC057676.1| Mus musculus cDNA clone IMA...
20 1 gi|727408|gb|U22929.1|MMU22929 Mus musculus anti-human...
21 1 gi|2500298146|dbj|LC762046.1| Mus musculus S737 ighv m...
22 1 gi|2211115670|gb|OM734675.1| Mus musculus isolate YFP...
23 1 gi|746427|gb|U22957.1|MMU22957 Mus musculus anti-human...
24 1 gi|746425|gb|U22956.1|MMU22956 Mus musculus anti-human...
25 1 gi|727402|gb|U22926.1|MMU22926 Mus musculus anti-human...
26 1 gi|727394|gb|U22911.1|MMU22911 Mus musculus anti-human...
27 1 gi|727390|gb|U22909.1|MMU22909 Mus musculus anti-human...
28 1 gi|727382|gb|U22905.1|MMU22905 Mus musculus anti-human...
29 1 gi|746423|gb|U22955.1|MMU22955 Mus musculus anti-human...
~~~
47 1 gi|1132625628|gb|KY199008.1| Mus musculus strain BALB/...
48 1 gi|1000379002|gb|KU256367.1| Mus musculus clone rPA013...
49 1 gi|45477409|gb|AY345161.2| Mus musculus clone B88-9 an...
```

2.4.3 Hit

Hit objects represent all the query results from a single database entry. They are the second-level container in the Bio.SearchIO object hierarchy. We've seen that they are contained by Query Result objects, but they themselves contain HSP objects.

```
>>> for hit in blast_qresult:
```

```
    hit
```

The above code will return a hit objects in the query result.

Output:

```
Hit(id='gi|262205317|ref|NR_030195.1|', query_id='42291', 1 hsp)
Hit(id='gi|301171311|ref|NR_035856.1|', query_id='42291', 1 hsp)
Hit(id='gi|270133242|ref|NR_032573.1|', query_id='42291', 1 hsp)
```

```
Hit(id='gi|301171322|ref|NR_035857.1|', query_id='42291', 2 hsp)
Hit(id='gi|301171267|ref|NR_035851.1|', query_id='42291', 1 hsp)
```

To check how many items hits in a Query Result holds, we can simply invoke Python's len method: len(blast_qresult)

2.4.4 High Scoring Point(hsp)

HSP (high-scoring pair) represents region's in the hit sequence that contains significant alignment(s) to the query sequence. It contains the actual match between your query sequence and a database entry. As this match is determined by the sequence search tool's algorithms, the HSP object contains the bulk of the statistics computed by the search tool. This also makes the distinction between HSP objects from different search tools more apparent compared to the differences you've seen in QueryResult or Hit objects.

```
>>> from Bio import SearchIO
>>> blast_qresult = SearchIO.read("my_blast.xml", "blast-xml")
>>> blast_hsp = blast_qresult[0][0]
>>> print(blast_hsp)
    Query: AR648815.1 Sequence 11 from patent US 6875433
    Hit: gi|255529870|gb|GQ162104.1| Mus musculus anti-beta-amyloid pepti...
Query range: [10:461] (1)
Hit range: [0:451] (1)
Quick stats: evaluate 6.2e-171; bitscore 614.43
Fragments: 1 (454 columns)
    Query - ATGGGCAGRCTTACWTCTTCATTCCTGCTGCTGATTGTCCCTGCATATGCTCTGTGYCCA~~~TTATC
           ||||| ||| ||||| ||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||| |||~~~ ||||
    Hit - ATGGACAGGCTTACTTCTTCATTCCTGCTGCTGATTGTCCCTGCATATGCTCTGTGCCA~~~CTATC
>>> blast_hsp.query_range
(10, 461)
>>> blast_hsp.evaluate
|
6.24552e-171
>>> blast_hsp.ident_num
409
>>> blast_hsp.gap_num
6
>>> blast_hsp.query_span
451
>>> blast_hsp.hit_start
0
>>> blast_frag = blast_qresult[0][0][0]
>>> print(blast_frag)
    Query: AR648815.1 Sequence 11 from patent US 6875433
    Hit: gi|255529870|gb|GQ162104.1| Mus musculus anti-beta-amyloid pepti...
Query range: [10:461] (1)
Hit range: [0:451] (1)
Fragments: 1 (454 columns)
    Query - ATGGGCAGRCTTACWTCTTCATTCCTGCTGCTGATTGTCCCTGCATATGCTCTGTGYCCA~~~TTATC
           ||||| ||| ||||| ||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||| |||~~~ ||||
    Hit - ATGGACAGGCTTACTTCTTCATTCCTGCTGCTGATTGTCCCTGCATATGCTCTGTGCCA~~~CTATC
>>>
```

3. Conclusion

We discussed the single function (Blast) using biopython but there are many function which can be executed by it, Biopython is a large open-source application programming interface (API) used in both bioinformatics software development and in everyday scripts for common bioinformatics tasks. The homepage www.biopython.org provides access to the source code, documentation and mailing lists. The features described herein are only a subset; potential users should refer to the tutorial and API documentation for further information. Biotechnology has many challenges and high data which is hard to handle manually, here comes the computational biology to make our job easier. So, Bioinformatics analyst or Data scientist whatever field you are learning biopython or other tools will make our jobs easier and faster.

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